

ODECO

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECosystem

D1.6 Training Week 4 “Towards an inclusive open data ecosystem”

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Abbreviations

DG DIGIT	Directorate-General for Informatics
BOSA	Belgian Digital Transformation Office
EU PO	European Union Publications Office
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
M	Month
MS	Milestone
NGI	(Belgian) National Geographic Institute
OD	Open Data
ODECO	Open Data ECOsystem
SB	Supervisory Board
TW	Training Week
WP	Work Package

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
Beneficiary			
1	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherlands
2	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	France
4	Universidad de Zaragoza	UNIZAR	Spain
5	Panepistimio Aigaiou	UAEGEAN	Greece
6	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	Denmark
7	Università degli Studi di Camerino	UNICAM	Italy
8	Farosnet S.A.	FAROSNET S.A.	Greece
Partner organisations			
1	7eData	7EDATA	Spain
2	Digitaal Vlaanderen	DV	Belgium
3	City of Copenhagen	COP	Denmark
4	City of Rotterdam	RDAM	Netherlands
5	CoC Playful Minds	CoC	Denmark
6	Derilinx	DERI	Ireland
7	ESRI	ESRI	Netherlands
8	Maggioli S.p.A	MAG	Italy
9	National Centre of Geographic Information	CNIG	Spain
10	Open Knowledge Belgium	OKB	Belgium
11	SWECO	SWECO	Netherlands
12	The government lab	GLAB	United States of America
13	Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure	ADSI	Denmark
14	GFOSS Open Technologies Alliance	GFOSS	Greece
15	Inno3 Consulting	IC	France
16	Regione Marche	RM	Italy
17	Open Data Institute	OCI	United Kingdom

1 Introduction

1.1 Training week program objective

The fourth Training Week (TW) of the ODECO project was organized by KU Leuven in between Brussels and Leuven. ODECO partners agreed in organizing the training week in the period April 15th-19th, 2023.

In defining the program of the week, the following relevant objectives/aspects were considered:

1. Feedback from the previous TW and needs expressed by the ESRs.
2. The description of the objectives of the TW in the DoA (Description of Action).
3. Deliverables that had to be delivered by the consortium in the upcoming period.
4. Involvement of external actors and of ODECO partners so to permit the exchange of ideas and point of views with people not involved in the ODECO project.
5. Inclusion of a social events to permit to the ESRs to enjoy some time together, and to reinforce the bindings among the ODECO partner members. With this regard, also considering feedback from previous TWs, it was decided to reduce the number of social events and devote more time and budget to training activities.
6. Inclusion of classes on relevant topics, as foreseen by the DoA.
7. Inclusion of a training that focused on skills acquisition.

In the following sections it is described how the organizational context, and the reported objectives were considered to setup the final program of the week.

1.2 Setup of the program

The first input that was considered, to derive the program of the TW4, was the feedback provided by the ESRs after the previous TW held in Ascoli Piceno. More specifically, ESRs suggested that was *"better to avoid on-line presentations"* and focus on *"practical and group activities"* and considering *"the possibility to interact with external experts/users"* as a *"must have"*.

Therefore, the organizers, in consultation with the Supervisory Board, decided to plan a TW that focused on **networking** opportunities, **workshops**, as well as specific **training** aimed at skills acquisition.

As per the **networking part**, taking stock of the comments received by the ESRs, it was decided to leverage on the contacts of the Public Governance Institute of KU Leuven with the EU Institutions, as well as the National Geographical Institute, and to organize the first day of the TW in Brussels. Before the training week, the ESRs were asked to provide a range of topics of their interest as a starting point for the discussions with the EU officials of DG DIGIT. The topics included: technical (data integration, data management, and data validators) and semantic interoperability (controlled vocabularies, metadata schemas, data models, domain-specific knowledge representation schemas and metadata evaluation frameworks), as well as legal and organisational interoperability. Also, the ESRs were interested in discussing perspectives on data spaces (and open data as part of them).

Different experts were invited to take part to the TW in two different **workshops** on how to achieve inclusive open data ecosystems. The first workshop was organized by the EU Publications Office, which is responsible for the European Open Data portal (data.europa.eu) and, more specifically, by Els Breedstraet, Head of Sector editorial services and outreach, and Nataliya Rozbroj Jasinskaja, Information and Knowledge Manager.

The second workshop was organized in cooperation with the Dutch National Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) committee, with five experts invited to take part to the TW. In particular, the following experts participated to the activity: Tessa Eikelboom, Wies Vullings, Jandirk Bulens, Hans Kooreman, and Cees Hof.

With the aim of improving communication and dissemination skills of the ESRs, Antonis Fourlis of FAROSNET was invited to organize a presentation on how to turn research into readings for the public and, more specifically, **how to write** engaging **blogposts**.

One of the objectives of the TW was to train the ESRs on challenges and opportunities for **project acquisition** in the context of open data. To achieve this goal, Henri Veldhuis CTO from SWECO Netherlands was invited to discuss the topic in the context of a transnational private organisation.

Finally, one key part of the organization of the TW was the provision of a training tailored on the needs of the ESRs. After internal consultations, it was decided that the ESRs could have benefitted from a training on **data visualisation**. Andrew Vande Moere, Professor of Design Informatics at KU Leuven, was identified as expert on the topic and he was asked to prepare a training based on specific requests of the ESRs that were collected before the training.

The setup of the program was also based on the objectives set up in the DoA. The following table provides an overview on how the general objectives of the DoA were implemented in the TW.

Table 1: General objectives of Training Week

Objectives of the DoA	Implementation in the TW
ODECO Network Day (day 1)	Day 2 (ESRs progress presentation to the ODECO Network), Day 4 (Social event)
ODECO Master Class IV (day 2&3), Inclusiveness: concepts, approaches, and public sector perspective and practices. Inclusiveness, Private sector perspectives and practices and citizens' perspectives and practices	Day 1 (BOSA and NGI), Day 2 (Workshop organized by the EU Publications Office on Inclusive Open Data Ecosystems) Day 3, (Workshop with the Dutch NSDI committee)
Professional Skills Training (day 4)	Day 5 (Training on data visualisation)
Communicating and disseminating research (day 4)	Day 3 (Blogpost writing session)
Project acquisition and funding, writing a business plan/case (day 4)	Day 4 (Project acquisition session with SWECO Belgium)
Outreach Event (day 5)	Day 1 (Meeting with the policymakers and EU officials at DG DIGIT, meeting at NGI), Day 2 (meeting with the EU Publications Office)

1.3 Location

The training week took place in different locations. The venues of the first day were DG DIGIT in Brussels, in the morning, and the Belgian National Geographic Institute (NGI), in the afternoon. The venue for the other days was room Couvreour in AGORA building of KUL in Leuven. The room was home of the ancient pharmaceutical institute, and it was chosen for its significant heritage, as well as the proximity with the train station and the city centre.

Figure 1 : The Future is Europe, wall painting outside DG DIGIT, photo by Ioanna Maratsi

Figure 2: Entrance of NGI, photo by Héctor Ochoa Ortiz

Figure 3: Room Couvreur, Social Sciences Campus at the KU Leuven, photo by Silvia Cazacu

1.4 Certificates of achievement

The SB agreed to issue a Certificate of Achievement for the training week at KUL for 50 hours workload as each country has different standards for what workloads reflect ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System). The Certificate of Achievement was given to all ESRs during the training week.

1.5 Supervisors attending the training week

Table 2: Supervisors attendance

Beneficiary	Supervisor name	Attendance
KU Leuven	Joep Crompvoets	In person, every day
TU Delft	Bastiaan van Loenen	In person, days 1-4
KU Leuven	Cesar Casiano Flores	In person, days 1-2
KU Leuven	Thérèse Steenberghe	In person, day 2
UNICAM	Andrea Polini	In person, days 2-4
UAEGEAN	Charalampos Alexopoulos	In person, days 3-4
UNIZAR	Francisco Javier López Pellicer	In person, days 1-4
FAROSNET	Antonis Furlis	In person, days 3-4
TU Delft	Anneke Zuiderwijk-van Eijk	In person, day 4
TU Delft	Marijn Janssen	In person, day 4
KU Leuven	Glenn Vancauwenberghe	In person, days 2-3
CNRS	Mélanie Dulong de Rosnay	Online, day 3
AAU	Birger Larsen	Online, day 4

1.6 Social Activities

To strengthen team building and networking between ESRs and, at the same time, avoid an agenda too crowded with social events, it was decided to organize two main social activities in Day 1 and Day 4.

In Day 1 it was organized a lunch at "Puro", a Portuguese restaurant that was located midway between the two venues of the training in Brussels (i.e., DG DIGIT and NGI). Els Breedstraet, the Head of Sector editorial services and outreach of the EU Publications Office, joined the social lunch. This gave the opportunity to ESRs to get to know an EU official working on open data policies implementation in an informal context.

Figure 4: Social lunch at Puro restaurant, photo by Ioanna Maratsi

In Day 4, a Belgian beer tasting, and contest was organized to introduce the participants to the culture and traditions of the area where the training was held, Flanders. They tasted various types of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beers while learning about the 26 monasteries of monks who dedicate their life to the beer making craft. Participants then discussed various types of beer making techniques which led to a team-based contest where representatives of each of the 3 tables competed in recognising beer types, pouring beer from the tap and general trivia questions. The beer contest was followed by a dinner where traditional Belgian food was served. The social activity took place at Brasserie Restaurant 't Oud Gasthuys, Leuven – located at a former pharmacy building in the city centre.

Finally, to promote interactions and networking, the TW launched the ODECO chocolate boxes. Filled with Belgian chocolate, the ODECO chocolate boxes were thought as token for the speakers of the event and as nice reminder of the ODECO project, serving as business card. The ODECO chocolate business card was highly appreciated by the participants of the training and favoured a relaxed environment, while functioning also as a promotion of the logo of the ODECO initiatives for external guests, such as the officials of DG DIGIT, the EU Publications Office, the Dutch SDI, to name a few.

Figure 5: ODECO branded chocolate boxes, photo by Héctor Ochoa Ortiz

2 Day 1 – EU institutions

2.1 Objectives, activities, and program

The first day of the training week aimed at opening a window on the work of the policymakers on open data related policies, to provide opportunities for networking, and to get to know the work of practitioners in one of the most developed open data fields, such as geodata.

The day started with a welcome from Alexandra Balahur, Team Leader Semic, DG DIGIT, that allowed ESRs and supervisors into DG DIGIT. Her opening was followed by an introduction of Joep Crompvoets (KUL), who provided some key facts on the ODECO project and invited a tour de table of the attendees. The introduction was followed by different presentations and Q&A sessions on from DG DIGIT that are of interest of the ESRs. More specifically, they first discussed the work of SEMIC regarding interoperability and the recent Interoperability Act. Then, they presented the work on Data Spaces, how they work in practice, how they integrate open data and what makes data spaces different from (open) data portals. Finally, the discussion shifted to Digital-ready policymaking and how data are integrated in the policy cycle. After a morning filled with presentations from EU officials, and a lunch break and social gathering, the afternoon session took place at the Belgian National Geographic Institute (NGI). Frank Leyman from BOSA welcomed the participants with an opening speech on inclusiveness of the open data ecosystem in Belgium, giving some examples of open data initiatives that could be relevant in connection to the topic of the TW. Then, Eric Bayers of NGI walked the participants through the activities and open data policies of the Belgian National Geographic Institute. His presentation was followed by a Q&A. Some takeaways from the conversation with Eric Bayers are the fact that some mobility-related open datasets are not considered as high-value-datasets and the lack of resources as an important limitation for open data sharing.

It is worth noting that Els Breedstraet, the Head of Sector editorial services and outreach of the EU Publications Office, decided to join the ODECO 'crew' for the first day of training in Brussels.

Table 3: Program Day 1.

* The person emoji represents that the activity happened in-person, while the computer emoji is used for activities with both in-person and online participants.

Time	Activity	
9:00 – 9:25	👤 Welcome at DG DIGIT 😊	<i>KUL (Joep Crompvoets as Coordinator)</i>
9:30 – 12:00	👤 DG DIGIT visit followed by presentations and opportunities for discussions. Main topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the work of SEMIC (the Semantic Interoperability group) • DG DIGIT work on Data Spaces • presentation on Digital-ready policymaking 	<i>Alexandra Balahur, Team Leader Semic, DG DIGIT</i>
12:15 – 14:15	Lunch at Puro, Rue Archimède 7, 1000 Brussels	<i>consortium</i>
14:30 – 16:30	👤 NGI (National Geography Institute) visit Opening from Federal Public Service Policy and Support (BOSA) on inclusive open data ecosystem in Belgium Eric Bayers (NGI)	<i>Frank Leyman, BOSA Eric Bayers, NGI</i>

Figure 6: Presentation on Linked Open Data at DG DIGIT, photo by Silvia Cazacu

Figure 7: At the NGI, during a discussion about the open data practices in the geo-spatial domain in Flanders, Belgium; photo by Ioanna Maratsi

3 Day 2 – EU Publications Office workshop

3.1 Objectives, activities, and program

The second day of the TW aimed at starting the discussion on inclusiveness as the key topic of the training and of the upcoming ODECO deliverables. To achieve this goal, in the month of February KUL invited two officials of the EU Publications Office to organize a workshop on Inclusive open data ecosystems based on their experience with the European open data portal (data.europa.eu). The workshop allowed to gather insights and ideas about how to make open data ecosystem, including data.europa.eu, more inclusive and useful for a wider range of users, including academic colleagues and other interested groups. The ESRs and supervisors, divided into four groups, were asked to elaborate on use cases that could address the lack of inclusiveness, then prepared a 5-minute presentation using a collaborative Miro board. From the workshop, four interesting case studies emerged:

1. "Eri, I have a problem": a data questioning chatbot for technical unskilled people who want to address some problems with data.
2. A community-based revisioning of datasets: Revising errors/inadequacies in existing datasets through technical artefacts and legal obligations.
3. Old & New Data Café: Connecting students with the elderly in a data café in order to help the elderly use open data to base decision making in their daily lives and improve data literacy skills in students.
4. Open data intermediaries for vulnerable communities: to address direct inclusions concerns of open data.

The case studies were then jointly discussed. The EU Publications office officials wrapped up the session reflecting on the case studies.

In the afternoon, the ESRs presented the progress of their research, using a 5 minutes presentation format.

Some highlights from the day were the interaction with the EU officials who shared relevant information on how data.europa.eu can host contents generated by the ESRs (e.g., blogposts or webinars) and how to apply to become an open data expert at the EU Commission.

Table 4: Program Day 2

Time	Activity	
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome, coffee	
9:30 – 11:00	👤 Workshop by EU Publications Office part 1/2 <i>Inclusive open data ecosystems.</i>	<i>Els Breedstraet, Head of Open Data Innovation and Outreach Nataliya Rozbroj – Jasinskaja Information and Knowledge Manager (Publications Office of the EU)</i>
11:00 – 11:10	Coffee break	

Time	Activity	
11:10 – 12:30	👤 Workshop by EU Publications Office part 2/2 <i>Inclusive open data ecosystems.</i>	<i>Els Breedstraet, Head of Open Data Innovation and Outreach Nataliya Rozbroj – Jasinskaja Information and Knowledge Manager (Publications Office of the EU)</i>
12:30– 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 – 14:45	👤 ESR progress presentations part 1/2 <i>Plenary presentations.</i>	<i>KUL (Coordinator) + consortium + EU Publications Office</i>
14:45– 15:00	Coffee break	
15:00 – 16:30	👤 ESR progress discussion part 2/2 <i>Plenary discussion.</i>	<i>KUL (Coordinator) + consortium</i>
16:30 – 18:00	Debrief, chat, networking opportunities (not mandatory)	

Figure 8: Silvia, Abdul, Ioanna and Alejandra (not in the picture) presenting their proposal for a Data Cafe that brings together students with the elderly to address issues with open data; photo by Georgios Papageorgiou

Figure 9: Discussions about the EU Data Portal moderated by Els and Natalya of the EU PO, photo by Silvia Cazacu

4 Day 3 – ODECO deliverables and project coordination

4.1 Objectives, activities, and program

The goal of day 3 was to discuss the work in progress of the ODECO consortium regarding current and future deliverables, setting the foundations for the final outputs of the program and reflecting on the impact of the project itself.

The day started with a presentation and MIRO board activity on deliverable 4.1 led by Héctor Ochoa Ortiz of UNICAM concerning motivations of non-governmental actors to become active contributors to the open data ecosystem. In continuity with the first session of the morning, Joep Crompvoets of KUL presented the structure, organization, and theoretical foundation of deliverable 4.3, regarding stimulating non-governmental data holders to share their data as open data using governance mechanisms.

To improve communications skills and facilitate dissemination of research results, the presentations on the deliverables were followed by a training organized by Antonis Furlis of FAROSNET on how to write blogposts. During the session, several ideas and tentative titles for possible blogposts were presented and discussed.

The afternoon of the day was devoted to discussing the overall results and impact of the ODECO project with presentations delivered by Charalampos Alexopoulos of UAEGEAN and Glenn Vancauwenberghe of KUL. In the second part of the afternoon, the project manager organized and led a session on administrative and organizational aspects of the project that was followed by the Supervisory Board meeting.

Table 5: Program Day 3

Time	Activity	
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome, coffee	
9:30 – 11:00	🗣️ Deliverables 4.1 (Motivation of non-governmental actors to become active contributors to the open data ecosystem) + Deliverable 4.3 (Stimulating non-governmental data holders to share their data as open data using governance mechanisms) <i>Presentation, brainstorming, and discussion.</i>	<i>Andrea Polini (4.1) and Joep Crompvoets (4.3)</i>
11:00 – 11:10	Coffee break	
11:10 – 12:30	🗣️ Blogpost writing training. <i>Active working session.</i>	<i>Antonis Furlis + ESRs</i>
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 – 15:30	🗣️ Road towards September 2025: what & how, results and impact (WP5 & WP6) <i>WP Presentation & Brainstorm</i>	<i>All (Supervisors and ESRs), moderated by Bastiaan van Loenen</i>
15:30 – 15:40	Coffee break	

Time	Activity	
15:40 - 16:30	👤 TUD project coordination team + ESRs	<i>TUD PC (Danitsja van Heusden- van Winden) + ESRs</i>
16:30 – 17:30	📺 Supervisory Board meeting. Video-conference room located at 2 nd floor (SW 02.163)	<i>Supervisors + ESR council</i>

Figure 10: Project coordination meeting between ESRs and Danitsja, our project coordinator; photo by Héctor Ochoa Ortiz

5 Day 4 – From SDI to ODE

5.1 Objectives, activities, and program

The first objective of Day 4 was to contextualize contemporary European open data practices in relation to geo-spatial data, a domain which has historically dealt with the need to open data in response to societal challenges in a European context.

This objective has been achieved by considering the following contexts:

- The context of European policy, with a comparison between the work on the INSPIRE directive in the geo-spatial domain and the current work on Data Spaces. The activities focusing on policy aspects are a presentation by Joep Crompvoets, and two collaborative sessions.
- The context of practices within national boundaries, exemplified by participants representing public organisations from The Netherlands who shared their experiences working on a regional and national level in a brief presentation by Bastiaan Van Loenen, followed by in depth discussions during the two collaborative sessions.
- The context of a trans-national private organisation, exemplified by a presentation by the company SWECO which presented challenges and opportunities for project acquisition in the context of open geospatial data.

The second objective was to update ESRs on the planning and description of tasks related to the upcoming deliverable on MOOC. Here, Anneke Zuiderwijk, the work package leader, facilitated a collaborative session where ESRs created several assignments for the MOOC platform. The next deadlines and expected tasks were also set during this session.

The third objective was to provide networking and team building opportunities for the ESRs, supervisors and the other participants of the day and for this a social activity followed by a consortium dinner was organized.

An overview of the exact activities as planned in the daily program is presented in Table 5.

Table 6: Program Day 4

Time	Activity	
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome, coffee	
9:30 – 11:30	📄 Project acquisition, business plans and new company values by SWECO. Presentation (online), in room AV 01.12	Henri Veldhuis
11:30 – 11:40	Coffee break	
11:40 – 12:45	👤 MOOC presentation. Presentation.	Anneke Zuiderwijk + consortium
12:45 – 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 – 14:30	👤 Dutch SDI part 1/4 Introduction Presentation and interaction facilitated by Joep Crompvoets and Bastiaan van Loenen	All ESRs, supervisors, Tessa Eikelboom Wies Vullings Jandirk Bulens Hans Kooreman Cees Hof
14:30 – 14:40	Coffee break	
14:40 – 15:20	👤 Dutch SDI committee part 2/4	Moderated by Bastiaan Van Loenen

Time	Activity	
(25 mins group discussion, 10 mins plenary)	<p>Topic 2. From a linear to a circular open data ecosystem</p> <p>Questions for breakout session 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can different actors contribute value back to the ecosystem? • What are potential (new) business models and financial models support value creation for all? • What lessons can be drawn from (the evolution of) SDI? 	
15:20 – 15:30	Coffee break	
15:30 – 16:05 (25 mins group discussion, 10 mins plenary)	<p> Dutch SDI committee part 3/4</p> <p>Topic 3. From an exclusive to an inclusive open data ecosystem</p> <p>Questions for breakout session 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who should contribute open data back to the ecosystem? • How to develop and implement incentive structures to motivate this? • What lessons can be drawn from (the evolution of) SDI? 	Moderated by Bastiaan Van Loenen
16:05 – 16:15	Coffee break	
16:15 – 16:30	Dutch SDI committee part 5/5	Wrap up by Joep Cromptvoets
Starting 18:00	Social activity (Belgian beer tasting and team contest) + dinner at <u>Brasserie Restaurant 't Oud Gasthuys</u> , Leuven	consortium

Figure 11: Groupwork presentations as part of the collaborative sessions between ESRs and practitioners in the SDI domain in The Netherlands, photo by Silvia Cazacu

Figure 12: Belgian beer tasting contest between Georgios, Jandirk and Silvia during the social activity, photo by Ioanna Maratsi

6 Day 5 – Data Visualisation

6.1 Objectives, activities, and program

The objective of this day was to provide ESRs with skills training related to Data Visualisation. The objective was achieved with a lecture by Andrew Vande Moere, Professor of Design Informatics where ESRs learned about the role of Data Visualisation to create knowledge that ultimately changes human behaviour based on informed decisions, as seen in Table 6. During the lecture, the participants engaged in discussions about visualisation design, cognitive and psychological aspects that influence how visualisations are perceived, the data-ink ratio and recent developments related to embellishments, as well as new research opportunities for data feminism and critical data visualisation.

Table 7: Program Day 5

Time	Activity	
9.00 - 9.30	Welcome, coffee, network	
10:00 – 12:00	👤 Data Visualisation <i>Presentation, discussion.</i>	<i>Andrew Vande Moere, <u>Research[x]Design (KUL) + ESRs</u></i>
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch, drinks, farewell (optional)	

Figure 13: Impromptu discussion at the end of the DataVIS training, exchanging contacts and experiences between ESRs and Andrew, photo by Silvia Cazacu

7 Evaluation, conclusion and recommendations

7.1 Evaluation

We present the results of an evaluation form circulated after the Training week to which all 15 ESRs responded (N=15, anonymized from S1-S15). The form asked the following question:

- What would you keep from this training week? Why?
- What would you remove from this training week? Why?
- Which activity of the training week resonated most with your interest?
- Would you like to suggest a specific activity for the next training week?

The results show that among the successful activities are the session with the EU institutions (6/15), because it helped ESRs "position their work in a wider context" (S1) and helped ESRs to "share projects and outcomes to policymakers and practitioners, and also for networking for our future" (S5) and the data visualisation training (4/15). Other activities mentioned were the NGI visit (1/15), the meetings with open data practitioners (4/15) because these meetings contributed "external views and insight on our project which are directly aligned with the current status in our topics." (S10).

By far, the activity that resonated most with the ESRs interests is the Data Visualisation training (9/15), since *"You could notice the professor's engagement, his knowledge of the topic, and his effort to share his knowledge"* (S13) and *"the designers in the group really appreciated it, while the others learned how to communicate with design better"*(S1).

While ESRs considered that most activities fulfilled their interests regarding the Training week, some ESRs did consider that the time allocated to deliverables should have been used on skills training, rather than planning (2/15), since *"The supervisors' meetings about coordinating the deliverables should be held only between them. They are not taking into account any of the ESR's comments. In the end, they are just disengaged from every deliverable, not even taking the time to give proper feedback and being very disrespectful of the ESR's opinions and work."* (S13). Moreover, *"The day in which we discuss the deliverables is in general disappointing. It is somehow clear that some supervisors are not engaged enough and that we could do better in terms of collaboration."*(S15). At the same time, ESRs considered that the blog post training was not related to their interests since "without a hands-on workshop it was not as useful" (S11).

7.2 Conclusion and Recommendations for the next Training Week

Based on our evidence, the training week was a success considering that the ESRs found that it overall "was a good balance between work and doable schedule" (S10), with topics and external participants that helped expand their own knowledge and network, position themselves and become critical of their work.

According to ESRs feedback, the next TW should focus on hands-on activities that engage them in collaboration and discussion, rather than passive presentations that they should attend.

Moreover, learning from the success of the Leuven training week, they prefer a more balanced schedule that prioritises condensed, but focused activities and leaves them enough time to refuel for the following day. Moreover, since the group is well knit, ESRs have no difficulties in planning their own social activities, therefore we found little need for more than one typical consortium dinner for socialization.

Finally, a list of specific recommendations made by ESRs:

- To invite members of the EU institutions related to the Digital ready policy, research topics of the JRC, EU Publications Office,
- To remain aligned with the proposed activities and format and keep timing promptly

- To focus on career development and professional skills training for the next steps after the PhD
- Among specific topics, to focus on GenAI, LLMs and their role for the future of open data

Figure 14: Group photo after the second day workshop with the EU PO: ODECO ESRs, Bastiaan, Javier, Cesar and Es and Nataliya from the EU PO, photo by Mohsan Ali

Figure 15: Group photo after the fourth day of collaborative meetings with the colleagues from the SDI domain in The Netherlands, photo by ODECO